

Jordanians' Reliance on Al-Jazeera's Coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian Conflict in Light of the Framing Theory

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Abstract: Al Jazeera is popular Arabic news networks. As a result of its worldwide implications, news coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict is one of the most important and closely watched issues in Jordan. This study aims to investigate Jordanian's reliance on Al-Jazeera coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict through: first, the extent to which the Jordanians rely on Al-Jazeera in its coverage of the conflict, and second, the periods during which the Jordanians follow the coverage. A questionnaire and a sample were used that included 200 Jordanians 100 males and 100 females, based on the media framing theory. The results showed a variation in the extent to which the Jordanians depend on Al-Jazeera's coverage, as it was found that the majority depend on the channel in its media and news coverage. The results also revealed that the evening period is the most watched period for the channel's coverage of the conflict.

Keywords: The Russian-Ukrainian war, The media, News coverage, Al-Jazeera media network, the Jordanian public, Media treatment, News framing theory, War reporting.

1. INTRODUCTION

In a world dominated by obfuscation, misinformation, distortion, prejudices, stereotypes, clashes of cultures and civilizations, racism, ignorance, the culture of exclusion of the other, and the raging struggle over image and public opinion, the individual in society questions the veracity of what he watches, hears, and reads. Where are the ethics, fairness, and objectivity in the media's reporting on current events, such as the war between Russia and Ukraine and other global conflicts? Where is the honesty and the overstatement? Where is the propaganda and where is the truth? What part does the media play in these situations? Instead of informing, educating, and educating the public opinion with the goal of dialogue, discussion, understanding, and putting out the fire of enmity, hatred, and hatred, will the media in times of wars and crises transform into machines to sow discord, intimidation, exaggeration, politicization, and manipulation? Conflicts, violent confrontations, wars, and other crises, including the global financial crisis and terrorism, are all present in today's globe. Each of these crises has extremely serious implications for the person, society, and the state. A person's perception, beliefs, behavior, emotion, physiology, attitudes, and points of view are all influenced by the media. Because the human mind does not stop working when it receives information from newspapers, textbooks, news programming on television, or websites, the media is crucial. All information is transformed by the mind into knowledge, conclusions, and new meanings and principles that apply to every element of life. Whether it is related to democratic, dictatorial, developed or developing countries, or other political systems, the media's practice during times of war and crises is the same regardless of media or political systems, and becomes similar as the media becomes a combination of public relations, psychological warfare, propaganda, manipulation, misleading, and distortion. Numerous ideas that explain the purpose and operation of the media have been reviewed in light of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict. Since the start of the conflict, numerous media entities (press, television channels, and websites) have dispatched correspondents to the front lines to capture the action on camera. As a result, audiences throughout the world have benefited from in-depth coverage from these stations and media publications.

According to media framing theory, the way something is presented to an audience is called a frame, and it shapes the decisions people make about how to interpret that information. Frames are abstract activities that arrange the meaning of the news content. The media framing analysis theory is a theory that investigates the conditions of the news message's effect. This theory is founded on the idea that media events and contents have no meaning until they are placed inside a media context and frameworks, where these frameworks arrange words, texts, and meanings and employ prevalent social experiences and beliefs.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The media does not make the news they provide, but others do, and when news comes to the media, it does not come by itself, but rather by correspondents, journalists, and other elements that are called the sources of the editorial material as news is either events or sayings that must be attributed to a source for credibility (Hazaymeh, 2023:354). The media is a long-range arrow that leaves no one untargeted (Al-Mizid & Hazaymeh, 2021: 9). Jordanian media has a significant impact on journalistic writing, particularly press stories, due to its extensive use of English language because language is a crucial means of communication and a basis for interaction because the human being is a social creature by nature that cannot live alone (Hazaymeh, 2023:27; Hazaymeh, 2023:77; Hazaymeh, 2022:96; Vanyushina & Hazaymeh, 2021:230; Hazaymeh & Vanyushina, 2020:190). Language has important role in the times of peace and war (Al-Mizid, et al, 2020: 193). Taradai (2014:67–79) aimed to expose the domestication of news i.e., the framing of news in a way that takes into account the audience's cultural background in the Ukrainian media's coverage of the South Ossetia war in 2008. Nygren et al., (2016: 1-17) analyzed the content of the prevailing media coverage in four countries: Ukraine, Russia, Poland and Sweden, where they conducted interviews with journalists in the media in the four countries and compared the media coverage of the war in Ukraine in 2014 in these countries, where the results of the study revealed significant differences in the framing of the conflict and portrayal of actors, the actors on the Ukrainian scene during the war and the selection of words across the national environments of each of the four countries, as well as highlighting the fundamental differences in approaches and perceptions of the war. In his study on the extent of the Jordanian public dependence on Al-Jazeera's coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict and its effects, Hazaymeh (2023: x) finds that the proportion of people who depend on Al-Jazeera's coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian war varies. In her study "Comparing coverage of the Ukrainian-Russian conflict in the BBC, the Guardian, Al Jazeera and the New York Times online news press, with reference to framing theory: Feb-April 2022", Gardner (2022:15) emphasized that Al Jazeera use language that fosters sympathy for Ukraine and the conflict's victims. Fariq and Bin Trad (2023:180) and Shaihab (2022:vi) researched Al Jazeera News Channel dealing with the Ukrainian-Russian issue using the channel's programs "Ma wara' al-khabar; Behind The News" and "el hassad; the Harvest", is particularly interested in the Russian-Ukrainian war, as well as the conflict framing that dominates this coverage by used information patterns such as expertise and reporting to enrich the conversation show. The core concept of framing theory is that an issue can be examined from several angles and interpreted as having significance for diverse values or considerations as the process through which people acquire a certain picture of an issue or reorient their thinking about an issue is referred to as framing (Chong & Druckman, 2007:104) as frames can be both independent and dependent variables in the framing processes (de Vreese, 2005:52).

3. DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

Throughout history, the media has been a major tool for managing wars and conflicts, whether as a means of mobilization, recruitment, creating a sense of courage, nationalism, and inspiration in the troops and citizens of the country to which it relates, as well as a means of psychological warfare, fabricating facts, and undermining the spirit of the opposing troops and citizens. The media's significance grew dramatically after the advent of online media and social networking sites, whereby it came to be the most crucial tool in what are known as the fifth generation warfare. Of course, the conflict between Russia and Ukraine was not an exception to this trend. Rather, it was a bright example of how the media was utilized to serve as an important way for controlling the conflict and war between the Russian and Western sides (supporting Ukraine), as the latter party, i.e. the Western media, handled the war as a political chance to promote hatred against Russia. Because the Russian-Ukrainian war has an influence on Jordan due to fears of rising oil and basic food costs, which impacts Jordanians' daily life, as Jordan imports more than 80% of its supplies. In addition, the existence of thousands of Jordanian citizens in Ukraine and Russian Federation has intensified the immediate effect of the war on Jordan, leading the Jordanian people to become increasingly interested in its news. Al-Jazeera Network played an important role in documenting the Russian-Ukrainian war and its aftermath, as this coverage was complemented with political and economic analyses aimed

primarily at Arab audiences, particularly Jordanians. As a result, this research is aimed to highlight the extent to which the Jordanian people relied on Al-Jazeera network coverage of the conflict between Russia and Ukraine by examining the two inquiries that follow.

1. The extent to which Jordanians rely on Al-Jazeera's coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict.
2. The most periods in which the Jordanian respondents follow Al-Jazeera's coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict.

The study population comprises of Jordanians who watch Al-Jazeera Network for news and information regarding the conflict between Russia and Ukraine. In order to answer the study queries, a representative sample of (200) people was recruited, divided equally by gender, with (100) males and (100) females ranging in age from 20 to 60 years old. The "questionnaire" instrument was employed to collect the sample's responses since it is the most appropriate tool in descriptive studies that use the survey method to collect information.

1. The extent to which Jordanians rely on Al-Jazeera's coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict.

Table (1). The extent of reliance of the Jordanian respondents on Al-Jazeera's coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict.

Extent of Reliance	Repetition	Percentage
Great Extent	115	57.5%
Middle Extent	45	22.5%
Low Extent	24	12%
No Reliance	16	8%
Total	200	100%

The data of Table No. (1) show that the largest percentage of Jordanian respondents relied on Al-Jazeera's coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict is within the great extent where their number is (115) respondents, with a rate of (57.5%) followed by those who depend on Al-Jazeera's coverage to a middle extent where their number is (45) with a rate of (22.5%) then those who depend on this coverage to a low extent where their number is (24) respondents, with a rate of (12%), and in the last place were those who did not depend on Al-Jazeera's coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict whose number is (16), with a rate of (8%). The fact that Al-Jazeera is considered one of the Arab media networks specialized in reporting big events and news such as wars, political crises, and others may explain the high percentage of Jordanian respondents' reliance on its coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict. Al-Jazeera network also has journalists and bureaus throughout the world. It aims to give constant coverage of events and analyses of them with the support of experts in the area; additionally, Al-Jazeera network enjoys strong credibility and high rate of watching in the Jordanian society.

2. The most periods in which the Jordanian respondents follow Al-Jazeera's coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict.

Table (2). The most periods in which the Jordanian respondents follow Al-Jazeera's coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict.

Durations	Repetition	Percentage
Morning	29	14.5%
Afternoon	38	19%
Evening	119	59.5%
Undetermined periods	14	7%
Total	200	100%

According to Table No. 2, the evening time has the highest percentage of Jordanian respondents who follow Al-Jazeera's coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict with (119) respondents at a rate of (59.5%), followed by the noon period with (38) respondents at a rate of (19%), and the morning period with (29) respondents with a rate of (19%), and those who follow Al-Jazeera's coverage of the conflict in undetermined periods come in last with (14) respondents and a rate of (7%).

The large percentage of Jordanians watching Al-Jazeera coverage of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict in the evening and in the afternoon periods is due to the fact that the vast majority of Jordanians end their day work at 3 p.m. and are at their homes after work in ministries, universities, schools, and most workplaces, in addition to the lack of televisions and Internet access in many workplaces for employees.

4. CONCLUSION

The Russian-Ukrainian conflict provided an excellent opportunity for global and local media attention. Since the beginning of the conflict, several media outlets have assigned correspondents to battle zones to record events firsthand, and the media sources such as press, television channels, and websites have collaborated to provide broad coverage to audiences all over the world. Al-Jazeera network channel which was launched on the first of November 1996, is one of the leading Arab news and media channels that enjoys very high viewing rates and strong credibility in the Arab world in general and in Jordan in particular. The media frame theory is one of the theories that deals with the media's handling of news and events and how to place them in frameworks and convey them to the public. The Russian-Ukrainian conflict is one of the global events that the Jordanian public follows and is interested in, as this study worked to investigate the Jordanian public's reliance on Al-Jazeera's media coverage of the conflict through two inquiries: first, the extent to which the Jordanian public relies on Al-Jazeera's coverage of the conflict, and second, the times when the Jordanian audience follows that coverage. The study found a difference in the extent to which Jordanians relied on Al Jazeera's coverage of the conflict events, as well as a variance in the times at which they follow that coverage.

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